

CRB-sex-ratio

September 26, 2022

1 CRB Pheromone Traps on Guam Catch More Females Than Males

The male:female ratio of CRB caught in cross-vane bucket traps baited with oryctalure (Chemtica) on Guam is significantly different from 1:1. More females are caught than males.

```
[1]: import pandas as pd
      from scipy.stats import binom_test
      import sqlalchemy
```

Create a connection to the Guam CRB trap database

```
[2]: conn = sqlalchemy.create_engine('mysql+mysqlconnector://readonlyguest:
      ↪readonlypassword@mysql.guaminsects.net/oryctes')
```

Get Total Males and Females

```
[6]: sql = 'SELECT SUM(male_count) AS males, SUM(female_count) AS females FROM
      ↪trap_visit'
      df = pd.read_sql(sql, conn)
      males = int(df.males[0])
      females = int(df.females[0])
      n = males + females
      print(f'{males=}({int(100*males/n)}%) {females=}({int(100*females/n)}%)')
```

```
males=8578(45%) females=10243(54%)
```

Get min and max dates

```
[4]: sql = 'SELECT MIN(visit_date) as min_date, MAX(visit_date) as max_date FROM
      ↪trap_visit WHERE visit_date > 0'
      df = pd.read_sql(sql, conn)
      min_date = df.min_date[0].isoformat()
      max_date = df.max_date[0].isoformat()
      print(f'{min_date=} {max_date=}')
```

```
min_date='2007-10-07' max_date='2016-05-09'
```

Perform binomial test

```
[5]: p_value = binom_test([males, females])
      print('Binomial test results')
      print(f'{males=} {females=} {males+females=} {p_value=:.5g}')
```

```
Binomial test results
males=8578 females=10243 males+females=18821 p_value=6.7194e-34
```

```
[ ]:
```